

S1 N_d - L slope across clusters for varying three month intervals

S1.1 NEA cluster

Figure S1. Variation in liquid water path (L) with respect to droplet number concentration (N_d) for the NEA cluster, based on monthly means for March, April, and May 2017, using five selected PPE members ($p = 0, 35, 89, 150, 210$; panels a–e). The regression line (red) in panels (a–e) represents the high- N_d slope (m_h) from the piecewise fit. Panel (f) shows the probability density function of N_d - L slopes (m_h) across all 221 PPE members.

Figure S2. Variation in liquid water path (L) with respect to droplet number concentration (N_d) for the NEA cluster, based on monthly means for June, July, and August 2017, using five selected PPE members ($p = 0, 35, 89, 150, 210$; panels a–e). The regression line (red) in panels (a–e) represents the high- N_d slope (m_h) from the piecewise fit. Panel (f) shows the probability density function of N_d - L slopes (m_h) across all 221 PPE members.

Figure S3. Variation in liquid water path (L) with respect to droplet number concentration (N_d) for the NEA cluster, based on monthly means for September, October, and November 2017, using five selected PPE members ($p = 0, 35, 89, 150, 210$; panels a–e). The regression line (red) in panels (a–e) represents the high- N_d slope (m_h) from the piecewise fit. Panel (f) shows the probability density function of N_d – L slopes (m_h) across all 221 PPE members.

Figure S4. Variation in liquid water path (L) with respect to droplet number concentration (N_d) for the NEA cluster, for three month intervals of December-February 2016-17 (DJF, panel a), March-May 2017 (MAM, panel b), June-August 2017 (MAM, panel c), and September-November 2017 (SON, panel d) using MODIS retrieved satellite data.

S1.2 ETA cluster

Figure S5. The probability density functions of N_d-L slopes (m_h) across all 221 PPE members for the ETA cluster, based on three month intervals of December-February 2016-17 (DJF, panel a), March-May 2017 (MAM, panel b), June-August 2017 (MAM, panel c), and September-November 2017 (SON, panel d). The corresponding satellite data based N_d-L slope value is marked in each panel with a yellow dashed line.

Figure S6. Variation in liquid water path (L) with respect to droplet number concentration (N_d) for the ETA cluster, for three month intervals of December-February 2016-17 (DJF, panel a), March-May 2017 (MAM, panel b), June-August 2017 (MAM, panel c), and September-November 2017 (SON, panel d) using MODIS retrieved satellite data.

S1.3 SEP cluster

Figure S7. The probability density functions of N_d-L slopes (m_h) across all 221 PPE members for the SEP cluster, based on three month intervals of December-February 2016-17 (DJF, panel a), March-May 2017 (MAM, panel b), June-August 2017 (MAM, panel c), and September-November 2017 (SON, panel d). The corresponding satellite data based N_d-L slope value is marked in each panel with a yellow dashed line.

Figure S8. Variation in liquid water path (L) with respect to droplet number concentration (N_d) for the SEP cluster, for three month intervals of December-February 2016-17 (DJF, panel a), March-May 2017 (MAM, panel b), June-August 2017 (MAM, panel c), and September-November 2017 (SON, panel d) using MODIS retrieved satellite data.

5 S2 Constrained parameter space

S2.1 NEA cluster

Figure S9. Probability density functions (PDFs) of 37 perturbed model parameters under four constraint scenarios: unconstrained (grey), N_d-L slope (blue), R23 (green), and combined constraint (purple) for the NEA cluster. Vertical dashed lines indicate the median of each distribution.

S2.2 ETA cluster

Figure S10. Probability density functions (PDFs) of 37 perturbed model parameters under four constraint scenarios: unconstrained (grey), N_d - L slope (blue), R23 (green), and combined constraint (purple) for the ETA cluster. Vertical dashed lines indicate the median of each distribution.

S2.3 SEP cluster

Figure S11. Probability density functions (PDFs) of 37 perturbed model parameters under four constraint scenarios: unconstrained (grey), N_d - L slope (blue), and R23 (green) for the SEP cluster. Vertical dashed lines indicate the median of each distribution.

Figure S12. Relative importance of individual model parameters in contributing to uncertainty in regional-mean RF_{ACI} for the NEA cluster during December 2016–November 2017 under different constraint scenarios (Unconstrained, N_d -L slope, R23, and Combined). Bar segments represent individual parameters, coloured by process type (orange–green shades for aerosol-related and purple–blue shades for cloud-related parameters). Numerical labels correspond to parameter indices listed in the right-hand legends, with numbers placed inside bars for parameters contributing more than 5% to the total variance within that scenario. All values are normalised to 100% per scenario and month.

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Figure S13. Relative importance of individual model parameters in contributing to uncertainty in regional-mean R_{FACI} for the ETA cluster during December 2016–November 2017 under different constraint scenarios (Unconstrained, N_d -LWP slope, R23, and Combined). Bar segments represent individual parameters, coloured by process type (orange–green shades for aerosol-related and purple–blue shades for cloud-related parameters). Numerical labels correspond to parameter indices listed in the right-hand legends, with numbers placed inside bars for parameters contributing more than 5% to the total variance within that scenario. All values are normalised to 100% per scenario and month.

Figure S14. Relative importance of individual model parameters in contributing to uncertainty in regional-mean RF_{ACI} for the SEP cluster during December 2016–November 2017 under different constraint scenarios (Unconstrained, N_d -L slope, R23, and Combined). Bar segments represent individual parameters, coloured by process type (orange–green shades for aerosol-related and purple–blue shades for cloud-related parameters). Numerical labels correspond to parameter indices listed in the right-hand legends, with numbers placed inside bars for parameters contributing more than 5% to the total variance within that scenario. All values are normalised to 100% per scenario and month.